

Morphology and topography of chitosan-Zn complex/PEO fiber mats influence cell viability and attachment

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:
Chitosan
Complexation
Electrospinning

ABSTRACT

Electrospun fiber mats with therapeutic potential show great promise as wound healing biomaterials. This study aims to compare the biophysical properties and biocompatibility of four different biodegradable fiber mats; namely chitosan and chitosan-zinc complex (ChiZn)/(polyethylene oxide) PEO fibers, each with either nanometer-sized (~200 nm) or micron-sized (~1000 nm) diameters. Zn was incorporated to impact antibacterial properties of the fibers, ChiZn was synthesized using the in-situ precipitation method, and the influence of zinc chelation on the material structure and morphology was assessed using XRD, FTIR, XPS, and EDX, documenting the complexation and homogeneous distribution of zinc. ChiZn was then blended with PEO for electrospinning in a benign solvent system and crosslinked with glutaraldehyde vapor. SEM was used to examine fiber morphology while AFM documented a correlation between the roughness and fiber diameter. The effects of topography and composition on the viability, adhesion, and proliferation of stromal cells and mouse fibroblasts were investigated, showing higher cell viability on mats composed of nanosized fibers, whereas complex fiber mats composed of micron-sized fibers exhibited reduced cell viability. SEM evaluations showed that cells spread only on the surface of the nanosized fibers, independently of the presence of Zn, while cell infiltration into the mats was observed for micron-sized fibers.

1. Introduction

Tissue engineering scaffolds with appropriate chemical composition, topographical features, mechanical stability, and biodegradability are essential to support cell development and tissue regeneration [1]. Among a variety of scaffold fabrication techniques, electrospinning has emerged as a notable method for scaffold fabrication, offering versatility and cost effectiveness [2]. The technique produces scaffolds with fibrous structure. The diameter of fibers could range from nano scale to microscale, which significantly influences the material-cell interactions [2,3]. The features of fiber mats can be tuned to structurally resemble native components of the extracellular matrix (ECM), thus enhancing cell attachment and proliferation [4].

Electrospun fiber mats from natural polymers, such as gelatin,

alginate and chitosan, have been widely used for biomedical applications [5]. Among them, chitosan stands out due to its favorable properties. Chitosan is a polysaccharide composed of randomly distributed *N*-acetyl D-glucosamine and D-glucosamine units [6], which share structural similarities with glycosaminoglycans (GAG) [7]. Chitosan exhibits several key properties that make it an ideal biomaterial for wound healing applications [8]. It is a biodegradable polymer that can degrade in-vivo through lysozyme activity [8]. The degradation products, *N*-acetylglucosamine and glucosamine which are chito-oligomers, can accelerate the wound healing process [6]. Chitosan contains free amino groups that can protonate under acidic conditions allowing it not only to dissolve at pH < 6 but also to serve as an effective antimicrobial agent. Low cytotoxicity profile of chitosan is another attractive feature: it is well tolerated by living tissues such as skin and nasal epithelium [9].

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Due to its hemostatic properties, chitosan is also preferred in commercial products approved by regulatory agencies, as a dressing material [10]. Many chitosan-based wound dressings are available on the market for clinical use [10]. Moreover, due to its functional groups, chitosan can be functionalized by the addition of biologically active agents to enhance its therapeutic potential.

Functional groups attached to the chitosan backbone, namely the hydroxyl (-OH) and amino (-NH₂) groups, are the main sites for chemical alteration [11]. These modifications can enhance chitosan's biomedical applications such as wound healing activity and antibacterial effect. Complexation of chitosan with metallic ions such as copper, gallium, and cobalt and its use for biomedical applications has been reported previously. Gritsch et al. [12] reported that chitosan-copper complexes showed excellent antibacterial activity against *E. coli* and *Staph. carnosus* without causing cytotoxic response from mouse embryonic fibroblasts [12] and a threefold increase of vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF) secretion from mouse originated stromal cells was also reported [13]. A strong inhibitory effect of chitosan-gallium complex on *E. coli* growth has been also observed, compared to undoped chitosan [14]. A recent study explored the use of chitosan-cobalt complexes in dentin-pulp regeneration: the complexes showed non-toxic behavior towards mouse fibroblasts and enhanced adherence of human dental pulp stem cells [15]. Cytocompatibility of chitosan-copper and chitosan-zinc complex aerogels with various concentrations of extracts of the complexes was investigated using a human embryonic kidney cell line [16]. Zinc showed a significant increase in cell viability compared to the same amount of copper incorporation as the use of copper is limited to only a narrow concentration range [16].

In this context, we showed in our previous research the potential of chitosan as a biologically active agent carrier for zinc [17]. Zinc successfully integrated into the polymer matrix, facilitating tunable release of Zn by varying zinc content. These ChiZn complexes showed strong antibacterial properties against *S. aureus*, promoted motility of human keratinocyte-like cell (HaCaT) and exhibited moderate anti-inflammatory effects with pro-inflammatory macrophages, making them a promising candidate for wound dressing material [17]. We hypothesized that ChiZn could be used in electrospinning technique to fabricate fibrous scaffolds that mimic the native architecture of the ECM, thereby supporting cell attachment and proliferation.

Besides the composition of biomaterials that stimulate specific functions, biological responses can be significantly influenced by the architecture of biomaterials. The topographical features of electrospun fiber mats can be easily tuned by altering experimental parameters, such as solution properties or operating conditions, to design a biomimetic structure. Scaffold characteristics like porosity, pore diameter, and fiber diameter are critical design parameters affecting cell attachment, spreading, proliferation, and differentiation [4,18,19]. Previous studies have highlighted the influence of surface features on cell responses [19–21]. For instance, Noriega et al. observed a correlation between fiber diameter and gene expression in bovine articular chondrocytes seeded on chitosan fibrous scaffolds with diameters ranging from 300 nm to 1 μm [20]. However, much uncertainty still exists about the interrelation between fiber topography and cell attachment, and the potential synergistic effects of surface topography with biochemical cues. To this end, this study exploits the topographical features of different diameters of fiber mats and examines the combined influence of materials chemistry along with topography on cell attachment. This study thus aims to compare biophysical properties and biocompatibility of four different biodegradable fiber mats: chitosan and chitosan-zinc complex (ChiZn) fibers with diameters either in the nano (~200 nm) or micron-size (~1000 nm) range. To achieve this, firstly chitosan-zinc complexes were fabricated by an in-situ precipitation method. Subsequently, ChiZn was blended with polyethylene oxide (PEO) to enable electrospinning in a benign solvent system. The fiber morphology was examined by SEM. The roughness of the fiber mats was measured by AFM. The effect of topography and composition of the fiber mats on the

viability, adhesion, and proliferation of stromal cells and of mouse fibroblasts was investigated, and the combined effect of the presence of Zn was discussed.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Fabrication of chitosan-zinc complexes

The preparation of chitosan-zinc complexes (ChiZn) was reported in our previous work [17]. Following the developed protocol [17], chitosan (4300, HQG 10, Primex Biochemicals AS, ChitoClear, Iceland) was dissolved in diluted (2 % v/v) acetic acid (AA, glacial acetic acid, >99.85 %, VWR, Germany) at a 2 wt% concentration at room temperature. After complete dissolution of chitosan, a predetermined amount of zinc chloride (BioReagent, Sigma Aldrich, Germany) was added to the solution to obtain 6 % saturation of functional groups of chitosan and the solution was stirred continuously for 2 h. Drop by drop, the homogeneous chitosan-zinc solution was added to a 0.5 M NaOH (VWR, Germany) solution. The produced chitosan-zinc complexes were stirred for 2 more hours. The samples were then separated via centrifugation and repeatedly rinsed with deionized water until they reached a neutral pH. The samples were then dried at 60 °C in an oven.

2.2. Fabrication and crosslinking of electrospun fiber mats

ChiZn complexes were dissolved in acetic acid (AA) by stirring for 48 h at room temperature. After obtaining a homogeneous polysaccharide solution, a predetermined amount of polyethylene oxide (PEO, MW: 900000, Sigma Aldrich, Taufkirchen, Germany) was added to the solution and stirred for 2 h. Prior to electrospinning, the solution was placed in an ultrasonic bath for 5 min to remove the bubbles in the solution. Identical protocol was used to prepare undoped chitosan/PEO fiber mats. Electrospinning was performed using a commercially available setup (Starter kit, Linari Engineering srl, Pisa, Italy). The solution was fed into a 3 mL disposable syringe (diameter 21G) and electrospun using a horizontal system with a flat target covered with aluminum foil. Table 1 summarizes the parameters used to produce different fiber mats together with their denominations. Chi-S and ChiZn-S refer to nanosized fiber mats, whereas Chi-B and ChiZn-B refer to micron-sized fiber mats. Since crosslinking is necessary due to immediate dissolution of the fiber mats when in contact with aqueous environment, glutaraldehyde (GA) vapor was used as a crosslinking agent. After electrospinning, the samples were removed from the aluminum foil and fixed with rectangular frames for crosslinking. The fiber mats were placed in the desiccator together with glutaraldehyde solution (25 % v/v) for 24 h, followed by 2 h evaporation under a fume hood to remove GA residual and stored for further usage.

Table 1
Overview of the parameters used to produce fiber mats.

	Chi-S ChiZn-S	Chi-B ChiZn-B
Chitosan concentration (wt %)	5	5
PEO concentration (wt%)	1	1,5
Solvent	Aq. solution of AA (50 % v/v)	Aq. solution of AA (90 % v/v)
kV	20	20
Distance needle tip-collector (cm)	15	12
Needle diameter (G)	21	21
Flow rate (mL/h)	3	3
Temperature (°C)	23–25	23–25
Relative humidity (%)	23–37	23–37

2.3. Characterization of complexes and fiber mats

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM, Auriga Base, Carl Zeiss, Jena, Germany) combined with energy dispersive X-Ray spectroscopy (EDX, LEO, 435VP, Carl Zeiss, Jena, Germany) was used to examine the presence and distribution of zinc in as-produced complex particles and complex fiber mats. X-ray Diffraction (XRD, PANalytical Empyrean, CuK α radiation, $\lambda = 1.5405 \text{ \AA}$) was performed after grinding ChiZn complexes using high energy ball milling (Fritsch, Pulverisette 5) at 250 rpm for 30 min, on ChitoClear chitosan and ChiZn complex powder to investigate the presence of possible crystalline phases and their changes after complexation with zinc. XRD patterns were recorded in the 2θ range between 5° and 80° at a step size 0.02° . For XPS analysis, a spot size of $400 \mu\text{m}$ was used. The survey spectra were acquired in the binding energy range of 0–1250 eV with an energy step size of 1 eV and a pass energy of 200 eV. High-resolution elemental XPS data were obtained using an energy step size of 0.1 eV and a pass energy of 50 eV. The morphology of fiber mats was examined using SEM-EDX on the surface of the mats coated with gold (Sputter Coater, Q150T, Quorum Technologies, Darmstadt, Germany). Based on the SEM images, the average fiber diameter of at least 50 randomly selected fibers was calculated using ImageJ (NIH, Bethesda MD) [22]. To investigate the functional groups of complexes and fibers. Fourier transform infrared (FTIR, Spectrum 3, Perkin-Elmer, USA) spectroscopy was applied. The spectra were obtained in the wavenumber range between 400 and 4000 cm^{-1} and at a spectral resolution of 4 cm^{-1} . AFM measurements were carried out using an AFM Bruker Innova instrument (Bruker, Santa Barbara, CA, USA). Three randomly selected image areas were acquired in tapping mode with a scan area of $50.0 \times 50.0 \mu\text{m}^2$ at 0.8 Hz scan rate to measure the roughness of the fiber mats (as a whole). To measure the roughness of individual fibers, firstly a scan area of $10.0 \times 10.0 \mu\text{m}^2$ was selected and then three random $1.0 \times 1.0 \mu\text{m}^2$ areas were chosen. The scan rate was set to 0.6 Hz. The topographic data were evaluated by the NanoScope Analysis software (Version 1.5, Bruker). To evaluate the stability of fiber mats, they were immersed in well plates containing 1 mL of cell culture medium. The well plate was incubated for up to 7 days and the medium was replaced three times. Afterward, the fiber mats were removed, washed, and air-dried. The morphology of the degraded fibers was examined by SEM.

2.4. Ion release

$$\text{Cell viability (\%)} = \frac{(\text{Absorbance of sample} - \text{Absorbance of blank})}{(\text{Absorbance of positive control} - \text{Absorbance of blank})} \times 100$$

The in vitro release behavior of the ChiZn complex/PEO fibers was determined in Tris/HCl buffer (Tris base, Sigma Aldrich/ACS, 37 % Sigma Aldrich, 50 mM, pH 7.4) and acetate/acetic acid buffer (99 % Sigma Aldrich/99 % Penta s.r.o. Czech, 0.1 M, pH 4.5) in the presence of $15 \mu\text{g/mL}$ lysozyme (hen egg-white, Sigma Aldrich). The fiber mats were cut with a surgical knife, fixed with inserts to immerse them in the solution (1 mg/mL) and incubated in lysozyme containing buffers in a shaking incubator at 37°C and 120 rpm. The dissolution media were collected at predefined time intervals (1 day, 3 days and 7 days) and a fresh buffer solution was added keeping the ratio of 1 mg/mL. The dissolution media were collected, stabilized with HNO_3 to pH ~ 2 and stored at 4°C before inductively coupled plasma optical emission spectroscopy (ICP-OES, Varian, Vista, MPX) measurement. For each sample, the experiments were carried out in triplicates. To deal with non-spectral interferences, the method of internal standard using an internal standard solution of Sc (10 mg/L) was applied. A series of at least three calibration solutions was prepared to obtain a linear

correlation between the measured signal intensity and the concentration of ions. The experiments were performed in triplicate.

2.5. Cell culture

Murine stromal cell line (ST-2, Leibniz-Institute DSMZ-Germany Collection of Microorganisms and Cell cultures GmbH, Braunschweig, Germany) and mouse embryonic fibroblast cell line (MEF, ATCC, SCRS 1040) were used for cell biology studies. Roswell Park Memorial Institute (RPMI, Gibco, Germany) and Dulbecco's Modified Eagle Medium (DMEM, Gibco, Germany) supplemented with 10 % fetal bovine albumin (FBS, Corning, USA) and 1 % Penicillin/Streptomycin (PS, Gibco, Germany) were used to culture ST-2 and MEF, respectively. Subsequently, cells were grown until they reached confluency and then detached by trypsinization and counted by trypan blue assay using hemocytometer (Roth, Germany).

2.5.1. Indirect and direct cell culture

Indirect biocompatibility of the fabricated fiber mats was determined by using ST-2 cells. Prior to the experiment, fiber mats were fixed with inserts (Cell Crown 24, Scaffoldex) and were disinfected by UV light for an hour and immersed in ethanol for another hour. It was ensured that the ratio of the fiber mat surface area to the volume of cell culture medium (1 mL) remained constant across all experiments. This was achieved by fixing the fiber mats in place using the inserts which standardized the amount of fiber mat exposed to the culture medium. Subsequently, the mats were washed with Dulbecco's phosphate-buffered saline (DPBS, Gibco, Germany) three times to remove ethanol residue. The electrospun fiber mats were immersed in 1 mL of complete cell culture medium for 24 h at 37°C . The resulting extracts, referred to as conditioned medium (CM), were then collected for further use. In parallel, 100,000 ST-2 cells were seeded in 24 well plates and incubated for 24 h. Subsequently, the medium was changed with CM and incubated for 48 h at 37°C in the cell incubator. The regular cell culture medium was used as a positive control. The viability of the cells was measured by incubating them with 1 % v/v of WST-8 reagent (CCK-8, Sigma Aldrich) for 3 h at 37°C . The absorbance was measured at 450 nm using microplate reader (FLUOstar Omega, BMG Labtech, Germany). All samples were measured in triplicate. The relative cell viability was calculated using the following formula:

To observe cell morphology, a fixation solution with paraformaldehyde in phosphate-buffered saline (PBS) was used for sample fixation. Then, the samples were rinsed with PBS and immersed in a permeabilization buffer containing Triton X-100, sucrose and PBS (Sigma, Germany). The cell nuclei were stained with $1 \mu\text{L/mL}$ DAPI, Thermofisher Scientific, Germany) and the cytoskeleton with $8 \mu\text{L/mL}$ rhodamine phalloidin (Thermofisher, Germany). The images were obtained by fluorescence microscopy (Axio Scope A1, Carl Zeiss, Germany).

To further assess the cytocompatibility, cells were directly seeded on the electrospun fiber mats. Before seeding the cells, sterilized fiber mats were incubated in complete cell culture medium (1 mL/well) at 37°C for 1 h, then the media was discarded. Drop seeding was performed by using an inoculum of 50,000 MEF or ST-2 cells in $100 \mu\text{L}$ drop per sample. $900 \mu\text{L}$ of complete cell culture medium was added after 3 h of incubation in a cell incubator to allow the cell to attach to the mats. After 24 h, the samples were transferred to a new well plate not to count the cells that

have grown on the walls of the well. The cell viability was measured after 1 and 7 days of incubation. The morphology of the cells on top of the mats was examined after fixing and dehydrating them gradually with increasingly concentrated ethanol solutions. Finally, the mats were dried in air at room temperature and coated with gold before examining them by SEM.

2.6. Statistics

The differences in analytical parameters between the different samples were analyzed by one way analysis of variance (ANOVA). The significance level was set at $p < 0.05$. For comparison of the mean values, the Tukey post hoc test was used.

3. Results

3.1. Characterization of the complex

Chitosan-Zn complexes were fabricated by the in-situ precipitation method, as described previously [17]. The incorporation of Zn was confirmed using FTIR, XRD, EDX and XPS. In FTIR spectra, chitosan exhibits a broad absorbance band ranging from 3600 to 3000 cm^{-1} , which is attributed to N—H and O—H bonds (Fig. 1a). The intensity of this broad band decreased and slightly shifted to higher wavenumbers upon chelation of zinc. The band at 1650 cm^{-1} was attributed to the C=O of the *N*-acetyl units of chitosan [23,24], while the band at 1550 cm^{-1} was ascribed to the bending of N—H groups [24]. The formation of coordination bonds between -NH₂ and Zn resulted in a slight reduction in the intensity of the peaks at 1650 cm^{-1} and 1550 cm^{-1} . The peak at 1405 cm^{-1} is commonly attributed to the C—N bond [25]. The most intensive peak was observed at 1028 cm^{-1} , which was attributed to the

Fig. 1. (a) FTIR spectra, (b) XRD diffraction patterns, and (c) EDX analysis of as produced chitosan zinc complex.

Fig. 2. (a) XPS survey scans, (b) high-resolution Zn 2p scan of as produced chitosan zinc complex, (c) high-resolution N 1s scan of as produced chitosan, and (d) high-resolution N 1s scan of as produced chitosan zinc complex.

glycosidic bond (C—O) of the glucosamine unit [25]. XRD analysis of chitosan confirmed its semi-crystalline nature (Fig. 1b). Upon complexation, ChiZn exhibited broader and less intensive diffraction maxima documenting its amorphous nature [26,27]. The EDX spectrum in Fig. 1c reveals three constitutional elements of chitosan, namely C, O, and N. In addition to those, the low intensity peaks at 1.0, 8.63 and 9.57 keV can be attributed to the presence of zinc. According to the EDX results, 6 % saturation of zinc resulted in 0.30 wt% Zn within the ChiZn complexes. The elemental mapping across the sample confirmed the uniform distribution of zinc.

XPS analyses were performed to gain more insight into the surface chemistry and oxidation states of the species. Fig. 2a shows the survey XPS scan for both chitosan and chitosan-Zinc complex. The scan confirms the presence of C, N, O, and Zn on the sample surfaces without any impurities. Additionally, the Zn 2p binding energies observed at approximately 1045 eV and 1021.9 eV correspond to the Zn 2p_{1/2} and Zn 2p_{3/2} components, respectively (Fig. 2b). The 23.1 eV splitting between Zn 2p_{1/2} and Zn 2p_{3/2} indicates the presence of zinc in the Zn²⁺ state [28]. Moreover, the N 1s peaks for Chi and ChiZn are shown in Fig. 2c and d, respectively. The major N 1s peak, with a binding energy near 399.4 eV, was assigned to non-protonated amine groups. In contrast, the higher binding energy region indicated the presence of protonated amine groups [29]. Upon zinc complexation, the high binding energy N 1s peak is mostly diminished, with the main peak appearing near 399.4 eV, suggesting the predominance of non-protonated amine groups [30].

3.2. Characterization of the fiber mats

3.2.1. Morphology

The morphological characteristics of as-spun chitosan-based mats and their fiber diameter distribution are presented in Fig. 3. With the

optimized processing parameters, all fiber mats showed continuous and uniform fiber structure with bead-free morphology. At the concentrations of <1 wt% of PEO, fibers could not be prepared under applied conditions and the process resulted in electrospinning (data not shown here). Since a flat target was used, the fiber mats showed a randomly oriented fibrous structure with a highly porous structure. The mean diameters of the nanosized fibers were $0.15 \pm 0.02 \mu\text{m}$ and $0.20 \pm 0.04 \mu\text{m}$, while the mean diameters of micron-sized fibers were $0.92 \pm 0.11 \mu\text{m}$ and $0.95 \pm 0.25 \mu\text{m}$ for undoped chitosan/PEO and chitosan-Zn complex/PEO, respectively. In addition to morphological examination of the as-spun fibers, the evaluation has been performed after GA crosslinking (Fig. 4). The crosslinking step did not affect the fiber morphology and diameter significantly: the mean diameters of the nanosized fibers were $0.20 \pm 0.04 \mu\text{m}$ and $0.24 \pm 0.04 \mu\text{m}$, while those of micron-sized fibers were $0.99 \pm 0.20 \mu\text{m}$ and $1.27 \pm 0.38 \mu\text{m}$ for undoped chitosan and chitosan-Zn complex, respectively.

AFM measurements were performed to determine the roughness of the fiber mats (as a whole mat) as well as the roughness of individual fibers. The surface roughness was expressed in terms of the root squared roughness (RMS) values. Fig. 5 compares the surface roughness of produced fiber mats (as a whole). A closer inspection of the figure shows that there is a correlation between the fiber diameter and RMS values: high roughness values were obtained in fibers with larger diameters. The RMS values of the fiber mats composed of nanosized fibers were $441 \pm 53 \text{ nm}$ and $303 \pm 87 \text{ nm}$ and those composed of micron sized fibers were $889 \pm 185 \text{ nm}$ and $1200 \pm 300 \text{ nm}$ for undoped chitosan/PEO and chitosan-Zn complex/PEO, respectively. Fiber roughness was additionally assessed to determine whether individual fiber roughness contributes to differences in roughness as a whole. The RMS values of nanosized fibers were $4 \pm 1 \text{ nm}$ and $7 \pm 3 \text{ nm}$ and the RMS values of micron-sized fibers were $18 \pm 1 \text{ nm}$ and $16 \pm 5 \text{ nm}$ for undoped chitosan/PEO and chitosan-Zn complex/PEO, respectively.

Fig. 3. SEM micrographs and mean fiber diameters of as-spun fiber mats.

3.2.2. Chemical and structural characterizations of fiber mats

To confirm the presence of zinc in the fibers, EDX analysis was performed. Fig. 5 shows an SEM micrograph and elemental EDX map of produced ChiZn complex/PEO fibers. The elemental mapping revealed that zinc was distributed evenly (Fig. 6). The constitutional elements of chitosan (carbon and oxygen) were also detected. Moreover, FTIR analysis was performed to understand the structural changes of blended fiber mats (Fig. 7). FTIR spectra of fabricated fibers were compared with those of the used raw materials (PEO and undoped chitosan) in Fig. 7. Chitosan showed its characteristic bands which were discussed in the previous section. The spectra are similar to the spectrum of undoped chitosan. However, some changes were observed due to the presence of a low amount of PEO in the structure. The intensity of the bands centered at 2883 cm^{-1} and 1340 cm^{-1} was higher than in the undoped chitosan [31]. Slight shift was observed for the bands at 1465 cm^{-1} and 1093 cm^{-1} . A new characteristic band at 840 cm^{-1} indicates the presence of PEO in the structure. Structural changes due to crosslinking with

GA were also observed in the FTIR spectra (Fig. 7b). The spectra of the mat with GA crosslinked exhibits a significant decrease of absorption in the regions between 3200 and 2800 cm^{-1} and 1700 to 800 cm^{-1} . A decrease of intensity and broadening of a band around 2872 cm^{-1} (attributed to C—H bonds) was observed, the intensity of a characteristic peak at 1070 cm^{-1} attributed to glycosidic linkage decreased, and the peak appears to be split. Even though the characteristic band related to amine groups (~ 1500 and 1600 cm^{-1}) did not seem to be affected, the intensity of the broad band around 3500 cm^{-1} , which is mainly associated with both primary amines and hydroxyl groups, decreased.

To investigate the stability of fiber mats, a degradation study was performed in complete cell culture medium (DMEM supplemented with 10 % FBS and 1 % PS). After 7 days of incubation, no degraded or eroded parts were observed (Fig. 8). Higher magnification images revealed no clear indication of any change in the architecture of the fibers. Additionally, the potential impact of ethanol on fiber stability has been evaluated through comparing the FTIR spectra before and after

Fig. 4. SEM micrographs and mean fiber diameters of fiber mats after GA crosslinking.

disinfection with ethanol for 1 h: the ethanol exposure did not cause any significant changes in fiber morphology or structure after the process (see also Fig. S1 in Supplementary information).

In vitro enzymatic degradation was performed to assess the zinc release from the fiber mats in the presence of lysozyme in acetate (pH = 4.5) and Tris buffers (pH = 7.4). A significant amount of Zn was measured on Day 1 indicating a burst release effect (Fig. 9). The release rate in both buffers then decreased, and the released amounts did not change significantly and stayed constant after Day 3. The release rates followed similar trends in all fiber mats with different diameters. The released amount of Zn was only slightly higher for nano-sized fiber mats, which was attributed to a greater surface area available for interaction with the solution for fibers with smaller diameters. Alongside the ion release studies, the weight loss study showed no significant differences in weight within 7 days of incubation.

3.3. Biological characterizations

To investigate the effect of complexation with zinc on cell viability, the dissolution products of fiber mats that have been immersed in RPMI medium for 24 h, were used. Fig. 10a shows the relative ST-2 viability after 48 h of incubation. Compared to the control group, the samples did not show any negative effect on the viability of ST-2 cells. The low magnification fluorescence microscopy images provide additional evidence supporting the positive response of ST-2 cells indicating that the cell densities were comparable with that of the control group.

To investigate the influence of the fiber diameter and complexation on the cell proliferation and spread, a direct cell study was performed using ST-2 and MEF cells. Fig. 11a presents the viability of ST-2 cells on top of the fiber mats after 1 and 7 days of incubation. An increment was detected in the absorbance values indicating that, with the exception of

Fig. 5. Atomic force microscopy images of the electrospun fiber mats and their root mean square (RMS) values.

ChiZn-B, the fibers supported cell proliferation. The viability of cells was significantly reduced with increasing fiber diameter. Also, the complexation with zinc negatively affected the ST-2 viability. After 7 days of incubation, undoped chitosan with nanosized fiber diameters showed the highest viability, whereas the complex micron-sized fibers showed reduced viability compared to the other groups. ST-2 cell morphology was visualized by SEM. Fig. 11b shows the cells adhered on top of the fiber mats after 1 and 7 days of incubation. The cells attached to the nanosized fibers in a 2D fashion, whereas infiltration of cells into the mat structure occurred in the case of microfibrillar mats already after 1 day of incubation.

Superior attachment of MEF cells at Day 7 was documented by the much higher absorbance values for all sample groups compared to Day 1 (Fig. 12a). No significant difference was observed between undoped micron and nanosized fibers while complexation with zinc had no negative effect on MEF cell behavior (ChiZn-S). However, after 7 days the metabolic activity of the cells attached on ChiZn-B was much lower compared to other groups indicating that cell proliferation was impaired. Similarly to ST-2 cells, cell infiltration was observed only in micron-sized fibers regardless of their composition (Fig. 12b).

Fig. 6. SEM micrograph and EDX mapping of ChiZn-S fibers (the data of other samples are comparable).

4. Discussion

Electrospun polymer fibers with therapeutic potential are valuable for biological applications, especially wound healing, due to their ability to mimic the structure of the ECM. Their functionality could be further enhanced through incorporating biologically active agents into the fiber mat structure. One of the approaches yields promising results through incorporation of nanoparticles (i.e. ZnO, Fe₃O₄, TiO₂, Au), improving cell viability, promoting angiogenesis and providing mechanical support for tissue regeneration [32]. With this aim, the present study deals with chitosan-zinc complexes blended with PEO and used to fabricate fiber mats by electrospinning intended as scaffold for wound healing.

To enhance the chitosan properties further, chitosan-zinc (ChiZn) was produced by an in-situ precipitation method reported in our previous work [17]. EDX analysis revealed the presence of Zn within the complex, with Zn uniformly distributed, as confirmed by EDX mapping. XRD patterns of ChiZn complex powders indicated the disruption of the semi-crystalline nature of undoped chitosan. This structural change can be attributed to the complexation between chitosan chains and Zn ions. This chemical interaction alters the inherent hydrogen bonding structure of chitosan, leading to the disruption of its semi-crystalline properties [26]. Upon the complexation with Zn, the alterations of the chitosan structure were reflected in the changes of FTIR spectra and Zn ion binding led to changes in both wavenumber and relative absorbance of specific spectral bands relevant to the interaction between chitosan and zinc. This assumption was further supported by XPS survey scan analysis which showed that ChiZn complexes exhibited one pair of new peaks attributed to Zn 2p (Fig. 2b). Zn 2p_{3/2} with binding energy of 1021.9 eV suggests the presence of zinc species in metallic form [33]. Additionally, the N 1s peaks were also affected by the addition of zinc (Fig. 2c and d). The nitrogen atoms in the amino groups can donate their lone pair of electrons to metal ions in the solution, facilitating the formation of complexes. Therefore, Zn—N bonds with functional group of chitosan led to the assumption that Zn is bonded with chitosan chains through -NH₂ [25,33,34]. The obtained complexes were highly stable after extensive washing with deionized water indicating a strong polymer-metal interaction. These findings are in agreement with previously published results [23,35]. For example, Lončarević et al. [35]

Fig. 7. FTIR spectra of fiber mats before (a) and after crosslinking (b) with glutaraldehyde vapor. Crosslinking is denoted as CL. Only the Chi-S spectrum is shown for clarity reasons. Spectra of the other samples are comparable.

Fig. 8. SEM micrographs of fiber mats after 7 days incubation in cell culture medium.

Fig. 9. ICP-OES results of cumulative Zn release from fiber mats incubated in acetate (pH = 4.5) and Tris buffer (pH 7.4) at 37 °C for 1, 3, and 7 days of incubation.

Fig. 10. a) Relative viability and b) fluorescence microscopy images of ST-2 cells exposed to dissolution products of mentioned fiber mats for 48 h (NS: $p > 0.05$). Fiber mats had been immersed in RPMI for 24 h and regular cell culture medium was used as positive control (indicated CNT). Scale bar: 50 μm.

fabricated bimetallic chitosan complex with copper and zinc. Similarly to this study, the complex formation was reflected in structural changes in the FTIR spectra and by the decreased crystallinity indicated in XRD patterns. Additionally, density functional theory calculations showed that both Zn and Cu aqua complexes, $[\text{Zn}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]^{2+}$ and $[\text{Cu}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]^{2+}$, form donor-type bonds with the amino groups in chitosan, leading to the formation of chitosan- $[\text{Zn}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]^{2+}$ and chitosan- $[\text{Cu}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]^{2+}$ complexes in aqueous medium. Complexation has been also reported for other metallic ions such as gallium, copper, iron, and cobalt [12,14,15,25]. A commonly accepted mechanism of the complexation process is described by Lewis acid-base theory: nitrogen atoms of $-\text{NH}_2$ in chitosan have a lone pair of electrons (act as a base) which are accepted by Zn ions (act as an acid) [11,23]. The proposed bridge and pendant models of chitosan-metal chelation is reported in the literature [11]. Moreover, as discussed by Wang et al. in the case of chitosan-Zn complexes, the molecular structure of chitosan-metal complexes could

Fig. 11. ST-2 cells on top of fiber mats: a) viability assessment and b) SEM images after 1 day (A-D) and after 7 days of incubation (E-H) (*: $p < 0.05$, NS: $p > 0.05$).

vary with different chelating ratios [23].

Electrospinning represents an area of growing interest in the bio-materials field due to its ability to produce nano and micron sized fibers [36]. The generated fibrous structures can be used in various tissue engineering applications [37]. Although mostly synthetic polymers are a primary focus for the technique, natural-based polymers such as chitosan have attracted attention due to their favorable properties, including biocompatibility, biodegradability, and antimicrobial nature. However, electrospinning of chitosan is rather challenging due to its polycationic

Fig. 12. MEF cells on top of fiber mats: a) viability assessment and b) SEM images after 1 day (A-D) and after 7 days of incubation (E-H) (*: $p < 0.05$, NS: $p > 0.05$).

nature, non-flexible chemical structure and strong intra and inter molecular interactions [36]. To overcome these issues, organic solvents such as trifluoroacetic acid (TFA), trichloromethane (TCM) or their mixture are commonly used in electrospinning of chitosan. However, their use limits the application of prepared fibers in biomedicine. Another successful and simple approach enhancing spinnability of chitosan is blending it with a second polymer such as polyvinyl alcohol (PVA), polyethylene oxide (PEO) or collagen [36,38]. In this study, PEO was used to improve the spinnability of chitosan: PEO is a bioinert, biocompatible polymer. A ratio of chitosan to PEO of 5:1 was used as a starting point to minimize the use of PEO without compromising the spinnability of chitosan, since lower ratios of PEO did not result in fiber

formation but rather in electro spraying, forming beads (data not shown here).

The properties of the initial electrospinning solution have a strong effect on fiber diameter and morphology. In this study, highly concentrated acetic acid solutions (50 % v/v and 90 % v/v) were utilized to obtain mats with different fiber diameters. A higher concentration of acetic acid is known to lead to an increased viscosity and decreased conductivity, resulting in production of thicker fibers. A similar effect was observed in this study: lower concentration of AA containing solutions (Chi-S and ChiZn-S) have significantly higher conductivity which leads to greater stretching of the electrospinning jet due to carrying more electrical charges, which in turn leads to a reduction in fiber diameter (Table S1). In parallel, the viscosity of Chi-S and ChiZn-S solutions is lower than that of Chi-B and ChiZn-B as they contain less concentrated AA (Fig. S2). Similarly, Varnaitė-Žuravliova et al. [39] measured a conductivity of 493 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ and a viscosity of 1.007 Pa.s for chitosan dissolved in 90 % acetic acid, 2240 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ and 0.615 Pa.s were determined respectively for 50 % acetic acid. Kriegel et al. [40] reported similar results suggesting that increased viscosity and decreased conductivity decreased whipping and bending instabilities, thereby making it possible to produce thicker fibers with smooth surfaces, yet with a broader diameter distribution range [40]. In the present study, a slightly higher amount of PEO was used (~ 6 wt% of total polymer concentration) to obtain significantly different fiber diameters, since a higher polymer ratio is known to lead to thicker fibers. On the other hand, polymer solutions with higher surface tension hinder the electrospinnability due to unstable jet formation that leads to generation of droplets whereas too low surface tension induces unstable jet formation and beaded fiber formation. Surface tension decreases from 73 mN/m for water to 28 mN/m for pure acetic acid at 20 °C [41]. In this study, both acetic acid amounts (50 % v/v and 90 % v/v) were able to decrease surface tension (Table S1). The electrospinning parameters applied in this study led to successful production of fibers with significantly different diameters without bead or ultrafine fiber formation which indicates that a stable jet and successful blending of the polymers were achieved. Similar fiber diameters and morphologies implied that complexation with zinc did not significantly affect the spinning process. Moreover, AFM results showed that the complexation did not significantly influence the local roughness of individual fibers. The roughness of fabricated mats (as a whole) composed of nanosized fibers was low and increased for the mats composed of the fibers of larger diameter (micron sized). The overall RMS values increased significantly with the increase of fiber diameters. This behavior was attributed to fiber thickness as well as the size of pores aligned with the surface of the mat [42]. The topographical properties and architecture of the mats were significantly influenced by the fiber diameter.

Glutaraldehyde (GA) is a well-established, highly effective and low-cost crosslinking agent for polymer systems such as gelatin, collagen and alginate. The crosslinking of chitosan with glutaraldehyde involves the reaction between chitosan's amino groups and glutaraldehyde's aldehyde groups, forming Schiff bases and covalent bonds. This process strengthens the chitosan structure, making it more stable and less soluble, with the formation of unsaturated bonds like imines and alkenes contributing to the crosslinked network [43,44]. Although a toxic effect on human health has been reported [45,46], its short-term application in vapor phase only results in low or non-detectable cytotoxic effect. A long term treatment of collagen/silk fibers with GA (48 h for example) caused a slight decrease in the proliferation rate of cells, reduced their adhesion and changed the cell morphology to more spherically shaped, whereas shorter treatments did not cause any negative impact [43]. In this study, the fiber mats were crosslinked by GA vapor for 1 day to reduce the risk of cytotoxicity. After crosslinking, the fiber mats showed a high resistance against rapid degradation in an aqueous environment. The stability test revealed that the crosslinking step was efficient, and all fiber mats preserved their stability and morphology for 7 days in cell culture medium at 37 °C.

The degradation behavior of tissue engineered scaffolds plays an important role in their performance as the kinetics may affect many cellular processes including cell attachment, spread and growth. Chitosan is known to be degraded enzymatically, mainly by lysozyme which exists in the body in various concentrations [47]. Degradation of chitosan is known to be controlled by the deacetylation degree of chitosan, concentration of the enzyme and the pH of the environment [48,49]. The high deacetylation degree (DDA) chitosan used in this study for fabricating the fiber mats should result in a slow degradation process of the fibers, as lysozyme targets linkage of β -(1-4) glycosidic bonds [8]. The availability of such bonds is limited. This could be considered an advantageous feature of the present fiber mats, since a fast degradation could trigger an acute inflammation reaction due to the production of an abundant amount of low molecular weight by-products within short time, leading to foreign body reaction [50]. pH profiles of healthy and wounded skin differ significantly: pH of health skin is slightly acidic whereas chronic wounds are reported to be at an alkaline pH [51]. The degradation assessment conducted in this study was carried out at two different pH values (4.5 and 7.4) to simulate health and wounded skin environments respectively, while the other parameters were kept constant. On the first day of incubation, a burst release of Zn was detected for all fibers at both pH values. This observation is in line with previous findings for Cu/Zn-chitosan complexes: the highest amounts of leached metal ions were detected in the first 6 h and the amount of released Zn was slightly higher than that of Cu due to the weaker complexation ability of Zn [35]. A quick Cu release has been reported in chitosan-copper complexes without the presence of enzymes in PBS, reaching the highest values after 10 h of incubation for various copper amounts before reaching a plateau [52].

The features of the mats structure significantly impact cell attachment, spreading, proliferation, and differentiation. The fiber diameter plays a crucial role in determining surface properties, including pore size and surface roughness, which tend to increase with larger fiber diameters [53]. Rougher surfaces promote protein adsorption, thereby enhancing cellular attachment and proliferation over time [54]. Kim et al. [42], investigated an early cell attachment on PCL fiber mats with a fiber diameter range from 0.1 to 3.4 μm . Superior cell attachment, spreading and metabolic activity were observed for the mats with thicker fibers, which was attributed to a higher surface roughness. The fibers with 110 nm diameter showed poor cell adhesion and spherical cell morphology was observed after 12 h of incubation [42]. On the other hand, PCL fibers of 750 nm diameter showed a significantly higher cell viability after 12 days of incubation compared to the fibers with diameters of 2, 4 and 6 μm . Cells seeded on the top of 750 nm fibers showed elevated gene expression compared to their thicker counterparts [55]. Noriega et al. [20] fabricated chitosan fiber mats with fiber diameters ranging from 300 nm to 1000 nm: fibers with 300 nm diameter showed higher cell density after 5 days of incubation and enhanced collagen II secretion was detected with decreasing chitosan fiber diameter [20]. In this study, the fibers with a diameter of approximately 200 nm showed higher ST-2 attachment on Day 1; the proliferation was also higher on Day 7. Similar results were obtained also for MEFs: nanosized fibers showed improved attachment and proliferation, yet the difference was not as pronounced as for the ST-2 cells. Besides cell attachment and proliferation, the influence of fiber diameter on the morphology of attached cells was observed on SEM images after 1 and 7 days of incubation. For the nanosized fibers, cell attachment was limited to the surface of the mat, whereas cells appeared to infiltrate throughout the whole fiber mat in the micron-sized counterparts. When the cells are seeded on the top of fibers with small diameter, the fibers are densely spaced in a planar manner with the distances between the individual fibers being smaller than the size of cells [18]. Unlike in a natural ECM environment, the cells then experience a 2-D growth profile without having the opportunity to infiltrate inside the fiber mat [18]. Such behavior was reported also in previous studies where increasing pore size of the fiber mats led to increased cell infiltration [55–57]. Reid et al.

[55] noted a strong correlation between fiber diameter and pore width in PCL fiber mats and an increased cell infiltration with increasing pore size. Enhanced cell infiltration was also observed for PCL/collagen/hydroxyapatite electrospun scaffolds with a larger pore size [57].

Another aspect that needs to be discussed along the topographical features is the sensitivity of the cells to surface chemistry, which significantly affects their behavior. The enhancement of cell attachment, growth, and spread can be attributed to cell-surface interactions which are mainly controlled by integrins present on the plasma membrane and surface non-polar and polar groups. The cell membrane mainly consists of lipids, embedded proteins, and water [58]. Since the cell membrane is negatively charged, the cell surface lipids can form hydrogen bonds with hydroxyl and carboxyl groups present on the surface [59]. For example, extracellular matrix fibronectin is adsorbed preferably on surfaces functionalized with $\text{NH}_3^+ > \text{CH}_3 > \text{COO}^- > \text{OH}$ [60] and adsorption of biomolecules and cellular attachment are affected by the surface properties. In this study, the surface chemistry of the fiber mat was changed by using chitosan-zinc complexes. Different results were obtained for different cell types: the viability of MEF cells was not significantly affected for ChiZn-S whereas significantly different activity of ST-2 cells was observed. ChiZn fibers with larger diameter (ChiZn-B) seemed to impair the attachment of both ST-2 and MEF cells. This effect was observed even on Day 1: the cell attachment was significantly lower than in the other groups. Longer incubation times did not improve the cellular response. It could be expected that the complexation with zinc improves cellular attachment since the cell membrane is negatively charged and tends to attach to positively charged surfaces [59]. Further investigations are necessary to precisely determine how complexation affects the surface physical, mechanical, and biochemical properties, as well as the protein adsorption on surfaces, and consequently, their impact on cellular response [61]. Nevertheless, the present results indicate a suitable experimental platform to assess the dual effect of topography and surface chemistry on cell behavior.

5. Conclusion

Blended chitosan/PEO was used to prepare fiber mats with nano and micro sized fibers, and the effect of the mat topography, morphology and chemistry on cell viability, attachment, and adhesion was studied. Electrospinning parameters were optimized to produce fibers of different diameters: a slightly higher PEO content favors fibers with larger diameters. The complexation of chitosan with zinc did not influence the optimized parameters of electrospinning: nano-sized and micron-sized fibers were obtained both from undoped chitosan and chitosan-zinc complexes. Crosslinking with GA vapors was applied to obtain fibers which are stable in an aqueous environment. SEM examination confirmed the fiber stability without morphological changes after up to 7 days of incubation in cell culture medium. In both compositions, higher fiber diameter resulted in mats with a significantly higher roughness. Indirect cell viability tests of the prepared mats confirmed their biocompatibility towards stromal ST-2 cells implying that neither released ions (from chitosan-zinc complex fiber) nor by-products from the process had cytotoxic effects. When the cells were seeded on the top of the fiber mat, their viability (both stromal cells and fibroblasts) was affected by topographical and compositional changes. In the case of fibers with larger diameters, the cells infiltrated through the fiber mat, while nano-sized fibers were only supporting the adhesion and spread of the cells on the surface.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Nurshen Mutlu: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Fatih Kurtuldu:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Validation, Investigation. **Aleksandra Nowicka:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Liliana Liverani:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology. **Dušan**

Galusek: Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Aldo R. Boccaccini:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgements

This paper is a part of dissemination activities of the project FunGlass. This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 739566 and the Slovak Recovery Plan under grant agreement No. 09I01-03-V04-00040/2024/VA. The financial support of this work by the grants APVV-19-0010 and SAS-MOST JRP 2018/02 are gratefully acknowledged. Dr. Kamalan Mosas and Dr. Si Chen (FunGlass, Alexander Dubček University of Trenčín) are acknowledged for XPS measurement.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2025.143394>.

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